

IMAGE SCRAMBLING ON A "MESH-OF-TORI" ARCHITECTURE*

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Abstract.

Recently, a novel method for image scrambling (and unscrambling) has been proposed. This method is based on a linear transformation involving the Kronecker-delta function. However, while quite interesting, the way it was introduced, leaves some open issues concerning its actual usability for information hiding. Therefore, in this paper, we extend the original proposal and show how it can be used to securely pass image-like information between the users.

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1. Introduction. Recently we observe a constantly growing interest in processing *multimedia content*. Here, the multimedia content is understood broadly and encompasses “still images” of all types, as well as video streams. Since a video stream can be viewed (with all understandable caution) as a sequence of still images (video frames), let us focus our attention on images, while keeping in mind that data processing may involve their sequences.

Observe that, there are two main sources of large images. First, sensor arrays of various types. For instance, one of the largest of them is the 2D pixel matrix detector installed in the Large Hadron Collider in CERN [14], which has approximately 10^9 sensor cells. Similar number of sensors would be required in a CT scanner array of size approximately $1m^2$, with about 50K pixels per $1cm^2$. Second, large data streams start to materialize in “consumer electronics.” For instance, currently existing digital cameras capture images consisting of 22.3×10^6 pixels (Cannon EOS 5D Mark II [3], as well as its successor Cannon EOS 6) or even 36.3×10^6 pixels (Nikon D800 [4]). What is even more amazing, recently introduced Nokia phones (Nokia 808 PureView [5], and Nokia Lumia 1020 [6]) have cameras capturing 41×10^6 pixels.

What has to be noted, from the point of view of computing (here, image processing), is that most of the existing sensor systems do not consider the natural arrangement of data. Specifically, the input image, which is square or rectangular, is “serialized” to be processed. Specifically, input data from multiple sensors is read out serially, pixel-by-pixel, and send to the CPU for processing¹. Next, after processing is completed, results are sent (serially) to a “display device,” where they are reassembled into a rectangular format. This means that the transfer of pixels destroys the 2D integrity of data (in computer memory, an image or a frame, exists **not** in their natural layout). As a result, the need to transfer large amount of data, from “multiple data input streams” to the processor, may prohibit development of applications, which require (near) real-time response [10].

Observe that, for the (near) real-time image / video processing, as well as a 3D reconstruction, it could be advantageous to process them using a device that has multiple processing units arranged rectangularly, and that allows to load data directly from the sensors to these units (for immediate processing). This would be possible, for instance, when a focal-plane I/O, which maps the pixels of an image (or a video frame) directly into the stacked “array of processors,” was to be used. Here, the computational elements could store the sensor generated information (e.g. a single pixel, or a block of pixels of a specific size) directly in their registers (or their local memory). Such an architecture would have three potential advantages. First, cost could be reduced, because there would be no need for the memory buses or a complicated layout of the communication network. Second, speed could be improved as the integrity of the input data would not be destroyed by the serial communication. Third, speed could be considerably improved by skipping the step of serialization of the rectangular image and, later, its reassembling in order to be displayed. As a result, data processing could start as soon as the data is available (i.e. in the registers / memory). Note that proposals for similar hardware architectures have been outlined, among others, in [9, 16, 26]. However, such approaches have not been tried in real-life. Furthermore, previously proposed focal-plane array processors were envisioned with a mesh-based interconnect between the

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¹Here, the term CPU is used broadly and encompasses standard processors, GPU's, Digital Signal Processing units, etc.

processing elements. This arrangement is good for the local data reuse (convolution-like simple algorithms), but is not the best to support global data reuse (matrix-multiplication-based complex algorithms).

2. Mesh-of-tori interconnection topology. This discussion leads us to the following question. Assuming that the focal plane I/O like approach is used to provide an effective data transfer to a rectangularly arranged group of processing units, what network topology should be used to connect them. Here, the experiences from development of parallel supercomputers could be useful. Historically, a number of topologies have been proposed, and the more interesting of them were: (1) hypercube – scaled up to 64000+ processor in the Connection Machine CM-1, (2) mesh – scaled up to 4000 processors in the Intel Paragon, (3) processor array – scaled up to 16000+ processor in the MassPar computer, (4) rings of rings – scaled up to 1000+ processors in the Kendall Square KSR-1 machines, and (5) torus – scaled up to 2048 units in the Cray T3D.

However, all of these topologies suffered from the fact that at least some of the elements were reachable with a different latency than the others. This means, that algorithms implemented on such machines would have to be asynchronous, which works well, for instance, for ising-model algorithms similar to these discussed in [8], but is not acceptable for most computational problems, that require synchronous data access. Therefore, an extra latency had to be introduced, for the processing units to wait for the information to be propagated across the system. Obviously, this effect became more visible with the increase of the number of processing units. At the same time, miniaturization counteracted this process only to some extent. Interestingly, supercomputers with some of the most efficient network connectivity, the IBM Blue Gene machines, combine the toroidal network with an extra networking provided for operations involving global communication (primarily, reduction and broadcast). To overcome this problem, recently, a new (*mesh-of-tori; MoTor*) parallel computer architecture (and topology) has been proposed. Let us now summarize this proposal. What follows is based on [20] and this source should be consulted for further information.

The fundamental (*indivisible*) unit of the *MoTor* system is a μ -Cell. The μ -Cell consists four computational units connected into a 2×2 doubly-folded torus (see, Figure 2.1). Logically, an individual μ -Cell is surrounded by so-called membranes that allow it to be combined into larger elements through the process of cell-fusion. Obviously, collections of μ -Cells can be split into smaller structures through cell division. For instance, in Figure 2.1, we see a total of 9 μ -Cells logically fused into a single macro- μ -Cell consisting of 4 μ -Cells (combined into a 4×4 doubly folded torus), and 5 individual (separate) μ -Cells. Furthermore, in Figure 2.2 we observe all nine μ -Cells combined into a single system (a 6×6 doubly folded torus; with a total of 36 processing units). Observe that, when the 2×2 (or 3×3) μ -Cells are logically fused (or divided), the newly formed structure *remains* a doubly folded torus. In this way, it can be postulated that the single μ -Cell represents a “holographic image” of the whole system.

Let us note that the proposed *MoTor* topology has similar restriction as the array processors from the early 1990’s. Specifically, the *MoTor* system must be square. While this was considered an important negative factor in the past, this is no longer the case. When the first array processors were built and used, arithmetical operations and computer memory were “expensive.” Therefore, it was necessary to avoid performing “unnecessary” operations (and maximally reduce the memory usage). Today (December 2013), when GFlops costs about 16 cents (see, [25]) and its price is systematically dropping; and when laptops come with 8 Gbytes of RAM (while some cell phones include as much as 64 Gbytes of flash memory on a card), it is the data movement / access / copying that is “expensive” (see, also [13]). Therefore, when images (matrices) are rectangular (rather than square), it is reasonable to assume that one could just pad them up, and treat them as square. Obviously, since the μ -Cell is a single indivisible element of the *MoTor* system, if the matrix is of size $N \times N$ then N has to be even (or padded to be such).

Note that in earlier publications (e.g. [20, 19, 18, 21]) the computational units, as well as the whole concept of the *MoTor* system, were purely “theoretical entities.” However, in [11] we have considered such system more closely, from the perspective of its potential realization. This line of reasoning resulted in the following proposal of the *computational unit* to be realized in the *MoTor* system. (1) It accepts input from the sensor(s) and transfers it directly to the operational registers / local memory. (2) Is capable of generalized fused multiply-add (*gfma*) operations, originating from various algebraic semirings (see, also [22, 1] for more details). The latter requirement means that, (3) the *gfma* unit considered here should store (in its registers) all constants needed to efficiently perform *fma* operations originating from various semirings. Finally, analysis of cell connectivity

FIG. 2.1. 9 μ -Cells fused into a single 2×2 "system," and 5 separate μ -Cells

in Figure 2.1 shows that (4) the *gfma* unit should include four interconnects that allow assembly of the *MoTor* system. Let us name such computational unit the *extended generalized fma*: *egfma*. Furthermore, let us keep in mind that the *MoTor* architecture is built from *indivisible* μ -Cells, each consisting of four, interconnected into a doubly folded torus *egfma* units.

Let us now observe that there are two sources of inspiration for the *MoTor* system: (i) processing data from, broadly understood, sensor arrays (e.g. images), and (ii) matrix computations. Furthermore, we have stated that the *egfma* should contain data registers to store (a) the needed scalar elements originating from various semirings, (b) data that the *fma* is to operate on and, as stipulated in [11], (c) elements constituting special matrices needed for matrix operations / transformations. Here, we have to take into account that each *egfma* should have a "local memory" to allow it to process "blocks of data." This idea is based on the following insights. First, if we define a pixel as "the smallest single component of a digital image" (see, [7]), then the data related to a single RGBX-pixel is very likely to be not larger than a single 32 bit number. Second, in early 2013 the (Tianhe-2) has 23,040,000 *fma* units² (see, [2]). This means that, if there was a one-to-one correspondence between the number of *egfma* units and the number of "pixels streams," then the system could process stream of data from 23 Megapixel input devices (or could process a matrix / image of size $N \simeq 4800$). This is clearly not enough. Finally, let us note that to keep an *fma* / *gefma* unit operating at 100% it is necessary to form a pipeline that is (minimally) 4-6 elements deep. Therefore, from here on, we will assume (and in this follow [19])

²Here, we count only the Intel Xeon Phi nodes. There are 48000 such nodes, each with 60, 8-way, cores, giving us a total of 23,040,000 double precision *fma* units

FIG. 2.2. 9 μ -Cells fused into a single 6×6 EG FMA system

that each computational unit in the *MoTor* system has local memory and thus be capable of processing blocks of data. For instance, a natural way of augmenting the *egfma* to achieve this goal would be to use 3D stacked memory [15].

Let us now consider the development of the *MoTor*-based system. In the initial works, e.g. in [20], links between cells have been conceptualized as purely abstract links (μ -Cells were surrounded by logical membranes that could be fused or divided as needed, to match the size of the problem). Obviously, in an actual system, the abstract links and membranes could be realized logically, while the whole system would have to be hard-wired to form an actual *MoTor* system (of a specific size). Therefore to build a large system with M^2 μ -Cells (recall the assumption that the *MoTor* system will have the form of a square array), it can be expected that such system will consist of silicon etched groups of μ -Cells residing on separate chips (μ -processors), combined into the *MoTor* system of a given size (similarly to multicore / multi-FMA processors combined into supercomputers).

As what concerns cell fusion and division, it will be possible to assemble sub-system(s) of a needed size, by logically splitting and/or fusing an appropriate number of cells within the *MoTor* system. However, it should be stressed that while the *theoretical* communication latency across the *MoTor* system is uniform, this is not likely going to be the case when the system will be assembled from μ -processors constituting physical macro- μ -Cells. In this case it may be possible that the communication within the μ -processor (*physical* macro- μ -Cell) will be relatively faster than between the μ -processors. Therefore, the most natural μ -Cell split should involve complete μ -processors. However, let us stress that the design of the mesh-of-tori topology *does not* distinguish between the connections that are “within the μ -processor” and “between μ -processors.” Therefore, the communication model used in the algorithms described in [20, 19, 11], and applied in subsequent sections, is *independent* of the

hardware configuration.

3. Fundamental operation. To proceed, let us note that, in what follows, we use the generalized matrix multiply-and-update operation (MMU) in the form elaborated in [23, 12, 11]:

$$C \leftarrow \text{MMU}[\otimes, \oplus](A, B, C) : C \leftarrow C \oplus A^{N/T} \otimes B^{N/T}.$$

Here, A , B and C are square matrices of (even) size N ; while the \otimes, \oplus operations originate from a matrix semiring; and N/T specify if a given matrix is to be treated as being in a standard (N) or in a transposed (T) form, respectively.

3.1. Reordering for the mesh-of-tori processing. Before discussing image processing, which is the main contribution of this paper, we have to consider the data input (e.g. from the sensor array, a medical scanner, or a cell phone photo camera) into the *MoTor* system. As shown in [20] (and followed in [11]), any input that is in the canonical (standard image / square matrix) arrangement, is not organized in a way that is needed for the matrix processing in a (doubly folded) torus. However, as shown in [19], the needed format can be obtained by an appropriate linear transform, through two matrix-matrix multiplications. Specifically, matrix product in the form $M \leftarrow R \times A \times R^T$, where A is the original / input ($N \times N$) matrix that is to be transformed, M is the matrix in the format necessary for further processing on the *MoTor* system, and R is the format rearranging matrix (for the details of the structure of the R matrix, consult [19]). Taking into account the implementation of the generalized MMU operation (see, equation 3), the needed transformation has the form:

$$M = R \times A \times R^T.$$

Note that, according to [20, 19], on the *MoTor* system: (a) operation $Z = R \times A$ is performed in place and requires N time steps, (b) operation $M = Z \times R^T$ is performed in place, and also requires N time steps and is implemented as a parallel matrix multiplication with a *different* data movement pattern than the standard multiplication. In other words, the matrix arrangement within the system remains unchanged for the transposed matrix operations, and the well-known problems related to row vs. column matrix storage (see, for instance, [17]) do not materialize (for more details, see [24]).

Observe that, when instantiating the *MoTor* system, it is assumed that an appropriate matrix R will be preloaded into the macro- μ -Cell, upon its creation (see, [11] for more details). Specifically, in addition to the operand registers dedicated to special elements ($\bar{0}, \bar{1}$) originating from selected semirings, appropriate elements of a transformation matrix, needed to perform operations summarized in [11] will be preloaded in separate operand registers. These operations include the transformation from the canonical to the "*MoTor* format" and back. Therefore, matrix R (of an appropriate size) will be preloaded into the *MoToR* system.

4. Image scrambling and unscrambling. Taking into account the background material presented thus far, let us focus on the main contribution of this paper. An interesting application of the matrix multiplication has been proposed in [18]. There, a linear transform, based on the Kronecker-delta function, was introduced. This transformation was then used to create a scrambling matrix C that could be used to scramble and unscramble images (via matrix-matrix multiplication). Since matrix denoted as " C " is very often used in different contexts (e.g. see, the above equation 3), for the purpose of this paper, let us re-name it as *SCRAM*. The complete description of the linear transform, as well as the specific structure of the *SCRAM* matrix can be found in [18]. Let us recall that, while the discussion below considers "single element per *gefma*" model, the real assumption is that a "data block per *gefma*" format is used (for more details, see [18, 19]). Therefore, all claims should be seen as actually concerning a *blocked data format*. Finally, we assume that image / matrix A is of size $N \times N$ (with N even).

Similarly to the processing needed to transform the matrix / image from the canonical to the *MoTor* format (and back), image (represented as a matrix A) scrambling consists of a triple-matrix product (forward transform): $S \leftarrow \text{SCRAM} \times A \times \text{SCRAM}^T$; where S is the resulting scrambled image/matrix. Unscrambling

of the same image (S) is a result of the following triple-matrix product (inverse transform): $A \leftarrow SCRAM^T \times S \times SCRAM$.

In [18], two ways to apply this approach to scramble images have been proposed. First, scrambling was to be applied $1 \leq J \leq N$ times to the whole image (matrix). The second approach was a “progressive” one. Here, one had to pick a key (parameter) $1 \leq K_P \leq N$. Next, scrambling was applied to the left top corner of the image, of size $K_P \times K_P$, $2K_P \times 2K_P$, and proceeded until the whole matrix was scrambled (in the case when N was not divisible by K_P then the complete matrix / image was scrambled in the last step).

In both cases, the scrambling operation could be realized by a $Scramble(A, nb)$ function. This function was to perform the tripe-matrix product involving the left top corner of size $nb \times nb$, where $1 \leq nb \leq N$. In the first approach, scrambling was achieved by calling the $Scramble(A, N)$ function J times. Observe that, on the *MoTor* system, each scrambling step would be performed in place, and would take $2N$ time steps. Therefore, the total cost of scrambling would be $2N \leq 2NJ \leq 2N^2$ time steps. Here, to unscramble the image without knowledge of the key K , would require knowledge of the matrix $SCRAM$, and applying the unscrambling operation J times (using function $ScrambleInv(A, N)$) until the original image was to be revealed (to the human observer).

In the second case, the $Scramble(A, nb)$ function would be called N/K_P times (and possibly one more time if N was not divisible by K_P). On the *MoTor* system, each scrambling step would cost $2K_P$ time steps (plus the cost of cell fusion, and of re-instantiating the $SCRAM$ matrix (for the next image / matrix size); however, these costs would be negligible in comparison with the cost of matrix multiplication). Therefore, the total cost would be between $2N$ (for $K_P = N$) and $4N - 2$ for (for $K_P = 1$) time steps. Here, recovering the original image would require knowledge of the matrix $SCRAM$, and searching space of all possible values of K_P , by applying the unscrambling function $ScrambleInv(A, nb)$.

Let us stress that the material presented in [18], while conceptually originating from the same roots (dense matrix multiplication), was not directly related to the *MoTor* architecture. Furthermore, it did not consider practicalities of use of the proposed transformation for secure image (multimedia) transfer / communication. Earlier, we have already made some comments about possible implementation of the scrambling (and unscrambling) procedures on the *MoTor* system, conceptualized as above (and approached as in [11]). Let us continue this line of reasoning.

First, let us make an obvious observation. The goal of image scrambling is to be able to *hide* the information (make the image unrecognizable to unauthorized persons), pass it to the authorized recipient, and reveal it by unscrambling. In this context, let us consider in some detail the implementation of the proposed image scrambling on a *MoTor* system. Here, the first approach involves initialization of the $SCRAM$ matrix (similarly to the R matrix mentioned above, and to other transformation matrices summarized in [11]). Note that, only a single $SCRAM$ matrix is going to be needed, as the scrambling procedure consists of application of the $Scramble(A, N)$ function J times to the whole image (matrix). As stated above, this approach is not safe at all. As soon as the potential attacker knows the $SCRAM$ matrix, (s)he can repeatedly apply the $ScrambleInv(A, N)$ function and after J steps the original image will be revealed. Furthermore, the computational cost of unscrambling will be the same as that of scrambling (assuming that the attacker also has a *MoTor* system at her/his disposal).

The situation is different in the second approach. Here, even the knowledge of the $SCRAM$ matrix, and the possession of the *MoTor* system, do not help the potential attacker sufficiently. Without the knowledge of the K_P parameter, the search space to uncover the information is much larger (though, obviously, the unscrambling is not impossible). However, this approach would be somewhat difficult to efficiently implement on a *MoTor* system (as described above, and in [11]). Observe that the recursive approach would require cell fusion. For instance, if $K_P = 64$ then the first scrambling would be performed on a block of size 64×64 (on a macro- μ -Cell consisting of 32×32 μ -Cells). Next, cell fusion would have to be applied (to create a macro- μ -Cell consisting of 64×64 μ -Cells, and matrix $SCRAM$ would have to be re-initialized, to apply scrambling to a block of size 128×128). In other words, let us assume that image of size 1024×1024 is to be scrambled, with the key $K_P = 16$. This means that the macro- μ -Cells of size 8, 16, 32, 64, 128, 256 and 512 would have to be used, and the $SCRAM$ matrices of sizes $N = 16, 32, 64, 128, 256, 512, 1024$ would have to be instantiated after each cell fusion. Note that the $SCRAM$ matrices cannot be preloaded, among others because the user can pick any value for K_P (even values that are not the most effective from the perspective of the *MoTor* system; including odd

values of K_P). Here, it should be stressed that, while use of odd values of K_P is possible, this does not match the concept of the *MoTor* system, where the μ -Cell is the fundamental computational unit. Furthermore, this also means that there is no natural way of utilizing the cell fusion and splitting that could allow dynamic creation of the *MoToR* systems that match the size of the scrambled block. Finally, note that padding, proposed above for the full-matrix operations, is not an option in an "internal step" of image scrambling, as the scrambling operation has to be performed on a block of data within an image (matrix).

Summarizing, while very interesting conceptually, ideas for image scrambling presented in [18] are not best suited for the *MoTor* architecture. Therefore, we propose a slightly different approach to image scrambling (and unscrambling), seen as a mechanism for information hiding (and safe transmission) on a *MoTor* architecture. Let us assume that two users would like to communicate multimedia content using the scrambling / unscrambling method discussed above. Observe that, for any matrix A , as long as the *SCRAM* matrix is known, the *ScrambleInv*(A, nb) reverses the effect of application of the *Scramble*(A, nb) function. This being the case, it is easy to see that all that is needed is that the sender applies the *Scramble*(A, nb) function a specific number of times (e.g. L times) for the selected values of nb . Next, it communicates to the receiver a tuple $(nb_1, nb_2, \dots, nb_L)$ that defines what were the values of nb_i used in each of the scrambling steps, and what was their order. Here, we assume that the *SCRAM* matrix is known to both the sender and the receiver. Next, the receiver applies the *ScrambleInv*(A, nb) function in an appropriate order (based on the known sequence of nb_i values) to recover the original image. A small "restriction" on this approach is such that at least one of the scrambling operations should involve the whole matrix A (as application of only blocked scrambling, without scrambling the whole image, leaves an unscrambled image strip; see [18, 19]). However, this approach makes it very difficult to unscramble the original image even if the attacker knows the form of the matrix *SCRAM*. The problem is in the fact that the sequence $(nb_1, nb_2, \dots, nb_L)$ can be completely "random," while being known only to the sender and the receiver.

The interesting part of this approach is in the fact that the number different blocks used in scrambling does not have to be large (as they can be repeated in the scrambling sequence) and that they can be defined in such a way to match the structure of the *MoTor* system. Here, let us recall that the size of the macro- μ -Cell can be dynamically adjusted through cell division and fusion. However, the image (matrix) A is stored across the whole *MoTor* system and this fact is not going to change. Let us now assume that the following scrambling sequence is to be applied $nb = 1024, 256, 512, 1024$ to a matrix (image) of size 1024×1024 . Here, it is possible (assuming that this is known in advance) to instantiate three *SCRAM* matrices in the *MoTor* system. Each element of these *SCRAM* matrices would be stored in a separate register. Now, the first scrambling would involve triple-matrix multiplication performed on the whole system. Next, the cell division would be applied to create a subsystem of size 256×256 (macro- μ -Cell consisting of 128×128 μ -Cells). Here, let us note that this subsystem would have preloaded *SCRAM* matrix of the correct size. In the following step, cell fusion would be used to create a subsystem of size 512×512 (macro- μ -Cell consisting of 256×256 μ -Cells); where an appropriate *SCRAM* matrix would be already preloaded. After the scrambling operation, cell fusion would be applied, again, to restore the original system, where the initial *SCRAM* matrix would still be available. Another triple-matrix multiplication would end the process. The unscrambling will proceed in exactly the opposite order, dynamically splitting and fusing the meta- μ -Cells and using the preloaded *SCRAM* matrices.

4.1. Object oriented implementation. In our earlier work (see, [23, 12, 11]), one of our goals was to develop a library of functions that will simplify writing codes for scientific computing applications (through application of matrix operations, represented in the style similar to that found in MATLAB / MATHEMATICA). In [11] we have introduced such a library, for a collection of operations involved in matrix / image manipulations, and supporting global reduction and broadcast operations. Obviously, there are multiple ways of implementing the proposed routines, and it is likely that such implementations are going to be vendor / hardware specific. Nevertheless, currently, object oriented (OO) programming is one of the more popular ways of writing codes in scientific computing and image processing. This being the case, we have conceptualized the top-level object oriented representation of the routines proposed in [11]. Since different OO languages have slightly different syntax (and semantics), we have used a generic notation, focusing on distinguishing information that needs to be made available in the interface and that to be placed in the main class. Here, we extend our proposal to include also scrambling and unscrambling operations. We start from the interface (see, also [11] for the

remaining matrices and operations that have been omitted in the snippets below).

```

/* T - type of matrix element */
interface Matrix_interface {
    public Matrix 0(int n) { /*generalized zero matrix*/}
    public Matrix I(int n) { /*generalized identity matrix*/}
    public Matrix operator + /*generalized A+B*/
    public Matrix operator * /*generalized A*B*/
    public Matrix Canonical_to_Motor(Matrix A);
    /*reordering for the mesh-of-tori processing*/
    public Matrix Motor_to_Canonical (Matrix A); /*inverse of
the reordering for the mesh-of-tori processing*/
    public Matrix Scramble (Matrix A,int nb);
    /*Matrix (Image) Scrambling*/
    public Matrix ScrambleInv (Matrix A,int nb);
    /*Matrix (Image) Unscrambling*/
}

```

This interface is to be used with the following class *Matrix* that summarizes the proposals outlined above.

```

class Matrix inherit scalar_Semiring
    implement Matrix_interface {
T: type of element; /*double, single, ...*/
private Matrix SCRAM (int n) /*scrambling matrix
private Matrix R (int n); /*matrix for MoTor
transformation*/
private Matrix ONES (int n) /* matrix of ones*/
private Matrix PERMUT(int i,j,n) /*identity matrix
with interchanged columns i and j*/
//anti-diagonal matrix of ones
private Matrix SWAP (int n)
// Methods
public Matrix 0(int n) { /*0 matrix*/}
public Matrix I(int n) { /*identity matrix*/}
public Matrix transpose(Matrix A){
/*MMU-based transposition of A*/}
public Matrix operator + (Matrix A,B)
{return MMU(A,I(n),B,a,b)}
public Matrix operator * (A,B: Matrix)
{return MMU(A,B,matrix_0 ,a,b)}
...
/*image scrambling*/
public Matrix Scramble (Matrix A,int nb){
return SCRAM * A * SCRAM^T};
public Matrix ScrambleInv (Matrix A,int nb){
return SCRAM^T * A * SCRAM};
...
private MMU(A,B,C: Matrix(n)){
return "vendor/implementer specific
realization of MMU = C + A*B where
+ / * are from class scalar_Semiring"}
...
}

```

Obviously, this class and the interface would allow writing codes in the suggested manner. Here, the matrix operations (image scrambling and unscrambling) would be performed by calling simple functions, and hiding all implementation details (including the existence of the matrix *SCRAM*) from the user.

5. Concluding remarks. The aim of this paper was to extend and modify a recently proposed novel method of image scrambling. The proposed improvements were made from the perspectives of (1) practical use of image scrambling for secure transmission of multimedia content, and (2) realization of the proposed method on the *MoTor* architecture. We have started from the rationale behind the need for efficient processing of large scale multimedia content and used this to outline the fundamental properties of the *MoTor* architecture. Next, we have introduced the image scrambling and unscrambling method proposed in [18]. This method was then analyzed from the perspective of its practical applicability, which resulted in the proposed modifications. Finally,

we have illustrated how the proposed approach fits into the object oriented realization of matrix operations proposed in [11]. In the future we plan to implement the proposed approach on the virtual *MoTor* system and study its efficiency.

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REFERENCES

- [1] *Kalray multi-core processors*. <http://www.kalray.eu/>.
- [2] *Top500 list*. <http://www.top500.org>.
- [3] *Canon EOS 5D*. http://www.usa.canon.com/cusa/consumer/products/cameras/slr_cameras/eos_5d_mark_iii, 2013.
- [4] *Nikon D800*. <http://www.nikonusa.com/en/Nikon-Products/Product/Digital-SLR-Cameras/25480/D800.html>, 2013.
- [5] *Nokia 808 Pureview*. http://reviews.cnet.com/smartphones/nokia-808-pureview-unlocked/4505-6452_7-35151907.html, 2013.
- [6] *Nokia Lumia 1020*. <http://www.nokia.com/global/products/phone/lumia1020/>, 2013.
- [7] *Wikipedia pixel*. <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pixel>, March 2013.
- [8] P. ALTEVOGT AND A. LINKE, *Parallelization of the two-dimensional ising model on a cluster of ibm risc system/6000 workstations*, *Parallel Computing*, 19 (1993), pp. 1041–1052.
- [9] S. CHAI AND D. WILLS, *Systolic opportunities for multidimensional data streams*, *Parallel and Distributed Systems, IEEE Transactions on*, 13 (2002), pp. 388–398.
- [10] D. FEY AND D. SCHMIDT, *Marching-pixels: a new organic computing paradigm for smart sensor processor arrays*, in *CF '05: Proceedings of the 2nd conference on Computing frontiers*, New York, NY, USA, 2005, ACM, pp. 1–9. doi:<http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/1062261.1062264>.
- [11] M. GANZHA, M. PAPRZYCKI, AND S. SEDUKHIN, *Library for matrix multiplication-based data manipulation on a "mesh-of-tori" architecture*, in *Proceedings of the 2013 Federated Conference on Computer Science and Information Systems*, M. Ganzha, L. Maciaszek, and M. Paprzycki, eds., IEEE, 2013, pp. pages 455–462.
- [12] M. GANZHA, S. SEDUKHIN, AND M. PAPRZYCKI, *Object oriented model of generalized matrix multiplication*, in *FedCSIS, IEEE*, 2011, pp. 439–442.
- [13] J. L. GUSTAFSON, *Algorithm leadership*, *HPCwire*, Tabor Communications (April 06, 2007).
- [14] E. H. M. HEIJNE, *Gigasensors for an attoscope: Catching quanta in CMOS*, *IEEE Solid State Circuits Newsletter*, 13 (2008), pp. 28–34.
- [15] P. JACOB, A. ZIA, O. ERDOGAN, P. M. BELEMJIAN, J.-W. KIM, M. CHU, R. P. KRAFT, J. F. McDONALD, AND K. BERNSTEIN, *3D memory stacking; mitigating memory wall effects in high-clock-rate and multicore CMOS 3-D processor memory stacks*, *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 97 (2009).
- [16] S. KYO, S. OKAZAKI, AND T. ARAI, *An integrated memory array processor architecture for embedded image recognition systems*, in *Computer Architecture, 2005. ISCA '05. Proceedings. 32nd International Symposium on*, June 2005, pp. 134–145.
- [17] M. PAPRZYCKI, *Parallel Gaussian elimination algorithms on a Cray Y-MP*, *Informatica*, 19 (1995), pp. 235–240.
- [18] A. RAVANKAR AND S. SEDUKHIN, *Image scrambling based on a new linear transform*, in *Multimedia Technology (ICMT), 2011 International Conference on*, 2011, pp. 3105–3108.
- [19] A. A. RAVANKAR, *A new "mesh-of-tori" interconnection network and matrix based algorithms*, master's thesis, University of Aizu, September 2011.
- [20] A. A. RAVANKAR AND S. G. SEDUKHIN, *Mesh-of-tori: A novel interconnection network for frontal plane cellular processors*, 2013 International Conference on Computing, Networking and Communications (ICNC), (2010), pp. 281–284.
- [21] ———, *An $O(n)$ time-complexity matrix transpose on torus array processor*, in *ICNC, 2011*, pp. 242–247.
- [22] S. G. SEDUKHIN AND T. MIYAZAKI, *Rapid*closure: Algebraic extensions of a scalar multiply-add operation*, in *CATA, 2010*, pp. 19–24.
- [23] S. G. SEDUKHIN AND M. PAPRZYCKI, *Generalizing matrix multiplication for efficient computations on modern computers*, in *Parallel Processing and Applied Mathematics*, R. Wyrzykowski, J. Dongarra, K. Karczewski, and J. Waśniewski, eds., vol. 7203 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2012, pp. 225–234.
- [24] S. G. SEDUKHIN, A. S. ZEKRI, AND T. MYIAZAKI, *Orbital algorithms and unified array processor for computing 2D separable transforms*, in *Parallel Processing Workshops, International Conference on*, Los Alamitos, CA, USA, 2010, IEEE Computer Society, pp. 127–134.
- [25] WIKIPEDIA, *Flops*. <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/FLOPS>.
- [26] Á. ZARÁNDY, *Focal-Plane Sensor-Processor Chips*, Springer, 2011.

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